

METADATA COLLECTION AT MICROSCOPY RESEARCH FACILITIES: OVERVIEW AND RECOMMENDATIONS

*WORK PACKAGE 4: BIG-DATA ELECTRON AND
CORRELATIVE MICROSCOPY FROM
INSTRUMENT TO PUBLICATION*

David POGER

AUSTRALIAN CHARACTERISATION COMMONS AT SCALE

MAY 2023

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.7949932](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7949932)

Dr David POGER

Microscopy Australia

Contact:

Dr David POGER

david.poger@micro.org.au

Australian Research Data Commons

This project is supported by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) and the following partners. The ARDC is enabled by NCRIS.

Contents

Executive summary.....	ii
1 Introduction	1
2 Metadata collection at microscopy facilities	3
2.1 <i>Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis (The University of Queensland)</i>	3
2.2 <i>Electron Microscope Unit (UNSW Sydney)</i>	5
2.3 <i>Centre for Microscopy, Characterisation and Analysis (The University of Western Australia)</i>	6
2.4 <i>Central Analytical Research Facility (Queensland University of Technology)</i>	7
2.5 <i>General observations</i>	7
3 Recommendations	8
3.1 <i>Metadata schema</i>	8
3.2 <i>Metadata properties</i>	9
3.3 <i>Metadata publication</i>	12
3.4 <i>Role of facilities in metadata collection</i>	12
3.5 <i>Role of institutions in metadata collection</i>	13
4 Conclusion	13
5 Acknowledgement.....	13
6 References.....	14

Executive summary

Metadata play a fundamental role in making research data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) by enhancing the discoverability, sharing and reuse of research data. They also increase confidence in the validity of the data by supporting research reproducibility. However, collecting metadata at microscopy facilities in a way that is sustainable and systematic has often proven challenging. The main barrier is the inability to extract information from the various systems used by facilities and universities throughout research projects (for example, in research data management plans and upon instrument booking). Many of these systems are part of the ecosystem of infrastructures provided by the universities that house facilities. In this report, five recommendations are proposed to foster best practices in metadata collection at microscopy facilities. These recommendations are based on the interviews of four university-based, microscopy research facilities and focus on five key elements:

Recommendation 1: Metadata schema

The preferred schema to use for general metadata is DataCite Metadata Schema.

Recommendation 2: Minimum metadata requirement

In the absence of specific requirements from stakeholder and funders, a minimum set of metadata properties called essential metadata properties should always be collected.

Recommendation 3: Metadata publication

Unless recommended otherwise by their institution, the researcher identified as the creator of the data is responsible for the publication of metadata via their institutional repository or an external repository that may be general or discipline-specific.

Recommendation 4: Metadata collection by facilities

Facilities should explore how the information required by metadata properties can be extracted from the different systems that they use for their operations (for example, facility management system, booking system, electronic laboratory notebook).

Recommendation 5: Institutional environment

Institutions should create and maintain an environment that allows for sustainable and seamless metadata collection through the provision of trained staff and interoperable information systems.

This work was undertaken under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication” of the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project.

1 Introduction

Metadata are often loosely referred to as “data about data”. They describe, organise and contextualise the data that they are affixed to by providing data or information on the preparation, experimental conditions, hardware, software, acquisition settings and analysis parameters that led to the described data. Typically, metadata describe what the data are (for example, a title, a description, keywords), how to use the data (for example, the data format, where to find the data or the publication supported by the data) and how the data are to be managed (for example, rights access, the relationship with other data or resources). A common analogy for metadata is the information on a package. The content of the package corresponds to the data whereas all the other pieces of information on the package (for example, the sender’s and recipient’s addresses, the importance or sensitivity of the package, postage, the date when and place where the letter was sent, and the symbols for the proper handling of the package during transit) are metadata. Metadata can provide a wealth of information on any attribute associated with the data. They are critical for making research data FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) [1] by facilitating research data sharing and maximising the likelihood of data reuse [2, 3, 4]. In particular, metadata are essential for machine-actionability, that is enhancing the ability of computational systems to automatically handle, use and interpret data with minimal or no human intervention.

The metadata of a resource are structured data that support functions associated with the resource. Structured data means that metadata follow a predefined, standardised format [5, 6]. Examples of metadata functions include data discovery, access, use, provenance, authenticity and security verification, preservation management and other activities throughout the data lifecycle. Importantly, such functions are established by drawing a relationship that someone claims to exist between a resource of interest and another identified object (for example, other data, a system, an organisation) through an attribute described in metadata called a metadata property [7]. As a consequence, as claims, metadata embed an implicit level of trustworthiness as to who makes the claims [7].

Metadata are often categorised as implicit or explicit [8]. Implicit metadata are data collected automatically, usually generated by a system (for example, the resolution information added to images by a camera), whereas explicit metadata are user-generated and encompass information purposefully added by a person (for example, annotation of an image). There is a general high-level consensus on three main types of metadata [9]:

- descriptive metadata: they support the discovery and general assessment of a resource (for example, its title, the names of its creators, its subject, keywords, a description, the language used in the resource);
- administrative metadata: they support technical (for example, file format, software information) and other operational aspects associated with the short-term and long-term management of the resource (for example, preservation, quality control, licensing, rights, access control, use requirements); and
- structural metadata: they support the linking among the components of a resource with other resources so that it can be fully understood (for example, relationship tags).

Note, there are various alternative classifications of metadata into several types and subtypes,

such as descriptive, technical, preservation, provenance and usage metadata [5]. However, in this report, metadata will be divided into two main categories: instrument metadata and general metadata. Instrument metadata are implicit, technical metadata generated by an instrument alongside and during (or after) acquisition of the data. They are embedded in the data files or gathered in separate files. There are many definitions for what an instrument is. In this report, a definition based on that proposed by the community of practice Identifiers for Instruments in Australasia (i4iOZ) is used and expanded [10]. i4iOZ defines an instrument as a piece of hardware, that is: *i.* a single instance of a tool, sensor or a device; *ii.* a sensor or individual measuring component on a single, complex instrument; or *iii.* a network, system or group of separate instruments that may be co-located or geographically distributed in space, but are connected through a single observation epoch [10]. Here, the definition of instrument is broadened to include software used to acquire, process and analyse research data. As a result, instrument metadata support research integrity and reproducibility in its three main aspects [11]:

- methods reproducibility: instrument metadata provide sufficient detail about data and procedures (during the experiment and analysis) so that the same procedures could be exactly repeated or recreated;
- results reproducibility: instrument metadata provide sufficient detail to obtain the same results from an independent study with procedures as closely matched to the original study as possible; and
- inferential reproducibility: instrument metadata provide sufficient detail about data and procedures (during the experimental and analysis) to draw the same conclusions from either an independent replication of a study or a reanalysis of the original study.

In contrast, general metadata are metadata that are not created by an instrument and provide general information. They are explicit metadata. They comprise data or information on the experiment, people, organisations, funding, publications, workflows, samples, specimens, rights, licenses, research subject, research field and any other data, information or research inputs or outputs associated with the described data. General metadata are essential to enrich data to a higher FAIR state and underpin research data discoverability, reusability and sharing.

A previous review on data management at electron microscopy facilities at Australian universities noted that metadata collection was overall disparate within a facility and between facilities [12]. Only metadata related to instruments (microscopes) were captured, with variations in terms of the nature and range of metadata across instruments, acquisition software and file formats. Microscopes often generated instrument metadata (for example, energies, scan time and lens and camera settings) that were embedded into data files (often in proprietary formats). However, it was noted that the conversion of these data files to open-source formats often entailed a loss of metadata. The conclusions of the review were consistent with the general observation that, despite the importance of metadata, the systematic collection of metadata has remained challenging for both researchers and microscopy research facilities for a range of reasons, especially: the lack of widespread, community-endorsed metadata standards; the lack of software tools to extract all available metadata; and the lack of workflows that collect metadata reliably, consistently, systematically and automatically [4, 13] The later requires scalable and adaptable software that integrates information from various sources into metadata, including electronic notebooks and instrument

schedulers or booking systems at facilities [3, 4, 14].

In this report, the collection of metadata at microscopy research facilities is examined. Note, only the collection of general metadata was investigated for two main reasons. First, instrument metadata were not considered because of the absence of widely adopted, community-wide metadata standards and conventions for the description and annotation of all electron-microscopy data. Second, general metadata are foundational to FAIR data. They have a direct relation with each of the four principles in FAIR (data findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability) so their capture is central in operationalising FAIR [4]. Based on the current state of the collection of metadata at four microscopy research facilities, the report focuses on the workflows and the data-management ecosystem that are essential to support a sustainable, systematic, consistent and automated capture of general metadata. Recommendations are proposed to promote good practices in metadata collection, facilitate the sustainable capture of general metadata and assist facilities and their host institutions in their journey to FAIR data.

This work was undertaken under the Australian Characterisation Commons at Scale (ACCS) project, in particular under Work Package 4: “Big-data electron and correlative microscopy from instrument to publication”. This report is intended as the conclusion of the work planned for deliverable WP4.11: “Develop guidelines for metadata collection”.

2 Metadata collection at microscopy facilities

Four facilities were interviewed about their current collection of metadata and their possible future plans about it, regardless of the nature of metadata (general or instrument metadata). Technological, operational and institutional barriers, if any, were also addressed. The four facilities that participated in this study were contacted after a call for expression of interest was sent to all the microscopy facilities associated with Microscopy Australia (core facilities or “nodes”, and affiliated linked laboratories). These facilities were: the Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis at The University of Queensland; the Electron Microscope Unit at UNSW Sydney; the Centre for Microscopy, Characterisation and Analysis at The University of Western Australia; and the Central Analytical Research Facility at Queensland University of Technology. In this section, a brief overview of the outcomes of the interviews are presented, followed by general observations.

2.1 Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis (The University of Queensland)

Instrument metadata and some general metadata are captured using the data-management tool Pitschi [15]. This is a significant change as it was previously the researchers’ responsibility to harvest and store metadata.

Pitschi is an end-to-end solution based on the data management framework Clowder [16] and designed for the Centre of Microscopy and Microanalysis in collaboration with the Research Computing Centre at The University of Queensland. It was developed as part of Work Package 4 in the ACCS project. It supports the entire research data lifecycle by storing, indexing and annotating data generated at the centre. Pitschi is fully integrated with the instrument-booking

system (Research Infrastructure Management System, RIMS) and the storage infrastructure (Metropolitan Data Caching Infrastructure, MeDiCI) at The University of Queensland. It facilitates or automates tasks from the capture of raw data to their ingestion and storage alongside automatic extraction and ingestion of metadata for supported file types from assorted sources (for example, data files, RIMS-based booking system and instrument computer). Data (or metadata) ingestion is the process of transporting data (or metadata) from one or more sources into a central location. Metadata can then be used for search and discovery. By design, Pitschi is compatible with the FAIR principles and contributes to enriching data to a higher FAIR state [17].

Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of the architecture of Pitschi, in particular how metadata are harvested and stored alongside data. Briefly, Pitschi is composed of several components which together participate in metadata collection and ingestion [15], namely:

- Clowder: this is a fork of the Clowder data management framework that extracts information from the RIMS API (application programming interface) about instrument bookings and projects. Amongst the various components of Clowder, some tools are relevant to metadata capture and management, and include Elasticsearch¹ to search metadata and a range of extractors that extract metadata out of ingested data files;
- XAPI: it extracts information from the RIMS API every 10 minutes for updates on bookings, projects and users, and uses this information as metadata;
- Pitschi-cli: this Windows desktop application sits on instrument computers, ingests data to a central repository and extracts metadata from the ingested data; and
- Pitschi-datamover: Where Pitschi-cli cannot be installed on an instrument computer because it isn't allowed by the instrument vendor (otherwise it could void the vendor's warranty) or because the instrument computer cannot be connected to the instrument network, a third-party computer connected to the instrument network is used for data movement with the desktop or web application Pitschi-datamover.

Metadata collection is flexible and expandable. As metadata extractors become available, they can be integrated into Pitschi. Additional metadata items such as identifiers related to organisations (for example, ROR IDs)², projects (RAiD)³ and instruments [10], could be harvested and ingested alongside the metadata currently collected.

Although the collection of metadata has progressed well with the successful rollout of Pitschi across a growing number of instruments at the centre, the publication of metadata has remained uncertain especially regarding where to publish metadata and who has authority to publish them. Metadata can be published in the university's institutional repository eSpace, but it is unclear whether eSpace can maximise data discoverability and access, and, therefore, enhance the FAIR state of the data enriched with metadata thanks to Pitschi. There is also confusion between the roles of eSpace and Research Data Australia (RDA).⁴ RDA is the national data discovery service of the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). RDA

¹ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>

² <https://ror.org>

³ <https://www.raid.org.au>

⁴ <https://researchdata.edu.au>

Figure 1 Schematic representation of the integration of the metadata collection in the architecture of Pitschi at the Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis (The University of Queensland). Metadata can be collected directly from the instrument computer using the application Pitschi-cli (A) or via a third-party computer using the application Pitschi-datamover (B). Adapted from Nguyen [15].

aggregates information and metadata from a range of sources and its online portal allows for finding research data. Individuals and organisations can publish metadata in RDA. As The University of Queensland contributes to RDA via eSpace, the roles of eSpace and RDA can appear redundant. Finally, at the time of writing this report, the university had no guideline as to who had the responsibility to publish metadata (for example, whether it was the researchers who acquired the data, the lead principal investigator or the university via the library).

2.2 Electron Microscope Unit (UNSW Sydney)

When instrument metadata are available, they are created automatically by the data-acquisition software. It is up to the facility's users to keep these metadata with their data.

General metadata are not collected. In general, UNSW Sydney has no policy on metadata collection. Nevertheless, there are opportunities that could be developed to collect and ingest general metadata. In particular, the Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre that houses the Electron Microscopy Unit (EMU) develops the laboratory information management system ACLS that is used by EMU and many other research facilities in Australia and worldwide.⁵ For example, information such as the researchers' names, the description of the samples, the funding sources and various identifiers (such as ORCID IDs, ROR IDs and instrument identifiers) could be harvested upon booking of instruments in ACLS (or through other features available in ACLS) and ingested as metadata. Complementary to ACLS, an electronic laboratory notebook developed by the university's Research Technology Services could be an additional avenue to collect general metadata (for example, description of the experiment and title of the data files). Metadata ingestion could then gather information from various sources at several stages of a research project, from instrument booking in ACLS to description of experiments and datasets in an electronic laboratory notebook.

2.3 Centre for Microscopy, Characterisation and Analysis (The University of Western Australia)

Metadata collection is currently the responsibility of the users of the Centre for Microscopy, Characterisation and Analysis. Although the University of Western Australia has no policy on metadata collection, there is a documented mechanism for staff and students to upload datasets and metadata on to the institutional data repository (UWA Research Repository). It requires manual entry on the part of the user and approval by data librarians prior to publication. It was noted that metadata input could be laborious. After approval, a digital object identifier (DOI) is minted to uniquely identify the metadata-enriched dataset. The approval process is manual and can be completed within 10 minutes (although the documentation states that the process to check and approve submissions could take 1–3 days). Data librarians indicated that if there was a large-scale increase in the uptake of this system or a large one-off push of metadata, they would be able to handle it. When a submission is refused, it may get bounced back to the researcher to check some of the information provided. The verification process currently focuses mainly on general spelling mistakes, presence and accuracy of license information, and that there are no obvious data security breaches.

The centre indicated that metadata collection was being explored using the trusted-data repository TruDat@UWA that is based on a local deployment of the data-management tool MyTardis [18]. It was initially created by a project led by the Australian National Imaging Facility (NIF) [19]. Data stored in TruDat@UWA are referred to as "trusted" because they fulfil specific requirements that certify their high quality:

- they were acquired on a "NIF-compliant instrument" that, amongst other criteria, has been assigned a persistent identifier (called the "Instrument ID");
- they possess minimal metadata such as date and time of acquisition, an identifier for the project that the data belong to, and the Instrument ID of the instrument the data was acquired from;

⁵ <https://www.analytical.unsw.edu.au/users/ac-lab-system>

- they include the native data generated by the instrument including the acquisition settings and parameters; and
- they include conversions to one or more open data formats when the native data are proprietary.

Building upon this project, NIF and Microscopy Australia proposed a standardised protocol for collecting quality data from characterisation instruments (project “Bringing long-tail microscopy and characterisation data into the light”). As a result, some metadata are captured for trusted microscopy data, but it has yet to be systematised for all microscopy data.

A notable metadata item that is collected is the persistent identifier for each instrument supported by TruDat@UWA. There was an initial development to push metadata from TruDat@UWA to UWA Research Repository and prefill many of the metadata fields. However, due to a loss in backend support for TruDat@UWA, this investigation was not completed. Note, the centre uses ACLS as its booking system so there is interest in future developments of ACLS that would enable the collection of metadata upon instrument booking.

2.4 Central Analytical Research Facility (Queensland University of Technology)

Metadata collection is the responsibility of the facility’s users. The amount and the type of the metadata harvested vary across users and projects. The facility uses ACLS as its instrument-booking system. While some information could be collected from it, the information entered by researchers upon booking is not in a consistent format. It is also siloed inasmuch as there is no information shared between ACLS and instruments or the university’s data store, the Research Data Storage Service (RDSS). Systematic and automated metadata collection would thus be challenging. Each instrument has a dedicated folder in RDSS. Once they are created, data are immutable and in read-only access to users. They are owned by the instrument that generated them, not by the person who operated or booked the instrument. As a result, if metadata are included in the raw data, they are never lost.

An opportunity that the facility considers for metadata collection is through the university’s Research Data Management and Primary Materials Checklist developed by the eResearch Office. The checklist has been especially used in the training of higher-degree-by-research (HDR) students to help them create data management plans for their research projects. The checklist contains mandatory fields (“Project Name”, “School” and “Faculty”) and optional fields about the project such as start and end dates, the researchers associated with the project (supervisors, collaborators) and fields of research. The checklist could then be used as source of information for metadata. In particular, as it is connected to other university systems, there is potential to crosslink researchers named in a project checklist to their ORCID identifiers.

2.5 General observations

There was a consensus across the four facilities interviewed that metadata and their collection were important. However, most facilities did not have the capacity to harvest metadata, except for instrument metadata, the collection of which was generally the responsibility of researchers.

All facilities found that the sustainable collection of metadata had to be seamless with limited

human intervention, which implied ingesting metadata from various sources in a systematic and automated way. This requires a level of interoperability between several systems that is often currently impossible. In particular, the information collected via the booking system of a facility, the institutional data repository and, if any, the electronic laboratory notebook, the data-management system or the laboratory information system used by the facility, is often siloed and cannot be shared with other systems. If metadata could be ingested from these various systems at different stages of a research project from the design of a research data management plan through to the booking of an instrument for an experiment and the description of data and samples in an electronic laboratory notebook, metadata collection would be sustainable and automated. The information may also be more reliable and consistent in both format and nature.

The successful development and implementation of the data-management tool Pitschi at the Centre of Microscopy and Microanalysis at The University of Queensland demonstrates that the interoperability of the different systems used by facilities is critical. The institutional environment also plays a central role in the ability to collect metadata. Indeed, many of the operations of a facility are embedded into or depend on the different infrastructures of its host university (for example, for instrument booking and data storage). In addition, institutional awareness on research data management and the FAIR data principles is fundamental. This was highlighted by all four facilities in the support received from university libraries or local e-research units. This greatly facilitates the journey of a facility towards metadata collection.

3 Recommendations

In this chapter, general recommendations on metadata collection are proposed to promote best practices across microscopy facilities and enrich data to a higher FAIR state. These recommendations are in fact applicable to all fields of research but are especially relevant to data-intensive research activities such as electron and correlative microscopy.

3.1 Metadata schema

The International Organization for Standardization defines a metadata schema (or scheme) as a “logical plan showing the relationships between metadata elements, normally through establishing rules for the use and management of metadata specifically as regards the semantics, the syntax and the optionality (obligation level) of values” [20]. In other words, a metadata schema facilitates the standardised description of a resource (for example, data) by establishing and defining characteristics of the resource known as metadata properties or metadata elements (semantics), as well as the rules for the use of these properties to describe the resource (syntax and optionality). A schema defines the type of content called a value that is permitted to describe properties. A value can consist of free text, controlled vocabulary (that is a limited set of defined terms allowed to be used as values) or an identifier. Importantly, as highlighted earlier, there is a level of trustworthiness in metadata [7]. How a person chooses to describe a resource using a set of metadata properties is not prescribed in a schema.

There is no one-size-fits-all for metadata and schemas. Schemas can be general-purpose (or generic) or specialised (specific to a discipline or field of research to address properties relevant to it). General-purpose schemas provide essential description of many different types

of resources for common metadata properties. They require limited expertise in the field of study. They are essential to enable FAIR data and foster data discovery, sharing and reuse. Specialised schemas may result in a better, more complete or more accurate description of data but they may need more time and expertise to provide the information that they required. Overall, general-purpose and specialised schemas are well-suited to general and instrument metadata, respectively. Given this report focuses on general metadata, only general-purpose schemas were considered. Several of these schemas are used across the research sector in Australia. For example, the Australia National University uses the generalised schemas Dublin Core⁶ for its institutional open-data repository ANU Open Research and the Encoded Archival Description (EAD) schema⁷ for its archives (ANU Archives) [21]. The University of Sydney also uses Dublin Core for its institutional repository (Sydney eScholarship Repository) whereas The University of Queensland uses the schema Registry Interchange Format: Collections and Services (RIF-CS) [22] for its institutional data repository eSpace [23]. Data collections in RDA are also described using RIF-CS so university data collections that are not based on the RIF-CS schema, such as ANU Open Research, need to be converted to RIF-CS to be harvested automatically for display and discovery in RDA. Although this adds a level of complexity, most common general-purpose schemas in research organisations, such as Dublin Core, RIF-CS and DataCite Metadata Schema [24], can be mapped to each other so interoperability is generally not a concern. ARDC is amongst the founding members of DataCite, a global organisation that provides persistent identifiers (DOIs) for research data and other research outputs [25]. DataCite Metadata Schema is the schema recommended by ARDC in the guidelines of its “Data Retention Program”.⁸

Recommendation 1: Metadata schema

The preferred schema to use for general metadata is DataCite Metadata Schema.

3.2 Metadata properties

The guidelines of the DataCite Metadata Schema defines three levels of obligation for metadata properties for the publication of metadata in the DataCite Metadata Registry [26]:

- mandatory metadata properties: they must be provided upon the submission of metadata;
- recommended metadata properties: they are optional but it is strongly encouraged to supply them alongside mandatory properties; and
- optional metadata properties: they provide a richer description of data.

Combined, mandatory and recommended properties enhance the discoverability of metadata and the findability of their linked data so the guidelines advise that they be submitted together.

This report follows this classification overall. Three levels of priority for the collection of

⁶ <https://www.dublincore.org>

⁷ <https://www.loc.gov/ead>

⁸ <https://ardc.edu.au/project/significant-national-data-collections>

metadata properties are defined based on their importance for microscopy data and their level of obligation for publication in the DataCite Metadata Registry (Figure 2):

- **essential metadata properties:** this is the minimum set of properties that should be collected if metadata are collected. This group overlaps with the mandatory set in the DataCite Metadata Schema guidelines so it allows for metadata publication in the DataCite Metadata Registry;
- **preferred metadata properties:** they are complementary to the essential properties. Together, essential and preferred metadata properties enrich data to a good FAIR level and ensures that the metadata can be properly indexed and found; and
- **additional metadata properties:** their collection may be of the lowest priority but when harvested, the FAIR state of the linked data is optimal.

Recommendation 2: Minimum metadata requirement

In the absence of specific requirements from stakeholder and funders, a minimum set of metadata properties called essential metadata properties should always be collected.

Ideally, the three sets of essential, preferred and additional metadata properties should be treated as incremental blocks of metadata to capture. However, only essential metadata properties constitute a single block that should always be collected when metadata are

Figure 2 Schematic representation of three levels of priority in the collection of metadata properties.

harvested. Preferred and additional metadata properties may be treated as as many individual targets to collect but with a higher priority for the preferred properties over the additional ones.

Table 1 lists the essential, preferred and additional sets of metadata properties. Details on the information to provide for every metadata property is available in the documentation of the DataCite Metadata Schema and is not discussed here [26]. It is important to note that some properties that are preferred or additional may have a higher obligation level for the stakeholders or funders that are associated with the research that generated the data. In this case, researchers should follow their guidelines. Table 1 shows that a few optional properties in the DataCite Metadata Schema are amongst the preferred properties because it is good practice to collect them wherever possible. For example, the property `alternateIdentifier` can be used for a local collection identifier using the naming convention of the researcher or the microscopy facility. Similarly, acknowledging the financial support that contributed to a research project is in general recommended or required by funders, so it is a good practice to include the funding information of the project that the data belong to in the property `fundingReference`.

Table 1 List of the essential, preferred and additional metadata properties.

Priority level	Metadata property	Comment ^a
Essential properties	<code>creator</code>	(M)
	<code>date</code>	(R); data creation and collection dates
	<code>description</code>	(R)
	<code>identifier</code>	(M)
	<code>publicationYear</code>	(M)
	<code>publisher</code>	(M)
	<code>resourceType</code>	(M)
Preferred properties	<code>title</code>	(M)
	<code>alternateIdentifier</code>	(O)
	<code>contributor</code>	(R)
	<code>date</code>	(R); any another date than creation and collection dates
	<code>format</code>	(O)
	<code>fundingReference</code>	(O)
	<code>geoLocation</code>	(R)
Additional properties	<code>relatedIdentifier</code>	(R)
	<code>subject</code>	(R)
	<code>language</code>	(O)
	<code>relatedItem</code>	(O)
	<code>rights</code>	(O)
	<code>size</code>	(O)
	<code>version</code>	(O)

^a (M), (R) and (O), Mandatory, recommended and optional property in the guidelines for the DataCite Metadata Schema [26], respectively.

3.3 Metadata publication

Metadata play a critical role in not only making research data FAIR, but also in supporting every stage of the data lifecycle (for example, for provenance, authenticity and preservation of data). Publishing metadata means making metadata properties available to external third parties (people and machines). It allows for information about data to become readily available. It thus fosters the discoverability of data. Metadata publication leads to the minting of a DOI (or another persistent identifier) that is linked to a landing page where all the information contained in the metadata is provided.

It is important to highlight that publishing metadata does not imply publishing data or granting access to data. The *publication* of metadata makes the existence of the data *public*. The level of public information given about the data is determined by the values attributed to the metadata properties that are published.

Recommendation 3: Metadata publication

Unless recommended otherwise by their institution, the researcher identified as the creator of the data is responsible for the publication of metadata via their institutional repository or an external repository that may be general or discipline-specific.

3.4 Role of facilities in metadata collection

Metadata can be captured at various stages of a research project; for example, when:

- a research data management plan is created;
- a project is created at a facility;
- an instrument is booked at a facility;
- data are acquired during an experiment;
- an experiment or data are described in an electronic laboratory notebook; or
- data are annotated in a data-management tool (such as OMERO [27, 28, 29]).

All the essential, preferred and additional metadata properties listed in Table 1 can be captured at one of these stages either automatically (for example, size and format of data) or ingested after the information has been provided by a researcher (for example, creator, date, description, title, fundingReference, geoLocation and language). Importantly, the information only needs to be entered once if it is collected throughout a research project, thereby making the process of metadata ingestion seamless, systematic, consistent and sustainable. This can be a determining factor to enable FAIR data.

Recommendation 4: Metadata collection by facilities

Facilities should explore how the information required by metadata properties can be extracted from the different systems that they use for their operations (for example, facility management system, booking system, electronic laboratory notebook).

3.5 Role of institutions in metadata collection

Institutions play an instrumental role in enabling facilities to collect metadata by:

- assisting facilities with trained staff (for example, e-research specialists, research data managers and data librarians); and
- creating and maintaining an ecosystem of infrastructures that allows for seamless and sustainable metadata collection.

The choice of an institution in the type of infrastructure (that is hardware, software and workflow) to support a function (for example, research data management, data storage, facility management system, booking system, electronic laboratory notebook) should take into account the interoperability of the infrastructures so that information can be shared between the different systems used for metadata ingestion. Siloed infrastructures create barriers to metadata collection, leading to the manual collection of metadata by researchers. This is tedious, impractical and unsustainable.

Recommendation 5: Institutional environment

Institutions should create and maintain an environment that allows for sustainable and seamless metadata collection through the provision of trained staff and interoperable information systems.

4 Conclusion

Metadata are essential to enable FAIR data. Yet, their collection at microscopy facilities has remained challenging. In his report, five recommendations are proposed to foster best practices in metadata collection at microscopy facilities. While some of the recommendations may appear simple, they can have far-reaching beneficial effects in the promotion of the FAIR principles, the harmonisation or standardisation of explicit, generic metadata in microscopy and other disciplines, and the implementation of interoperable information systems across universities that will facilitate information sharing.

5 Acknowledgement

The author would like to thank the staff at the facilities and universities who were interviewed on their current and future plans for metadata collection; namely: Dr Emily Barker and A/Prof Martin Saunders at the Centre for Microscopy, Characterisation and Analysis, The University of Western Australia; Dr Rubbiya Ali, Dr Hoang Nguyen and Prof Roger Wepf at the Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis, The University of Queensland; A/Prof Jamie Riches at the Central Analytical Research Facility, and Prof Matthew Bellgard at the eResearch Office, Queensland University of Technology; Craig Windell at Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation; and Dr Richard Webster and Dr Yin Yao at the Electron Microscope Unit, Dongming Zheng at Mark Wainwright Analytical Centre, and Duncan Smith at Research Technology Services, UNSW Sydney.

6 References

- 1 Wilkinson, M. D., Dumontier, M., Aalbersberg, I. J., Appleton, G., Axton, M., Baak, A., Blomberg, N., Boiten, J.-W., da Silva Santos, L. B., Bourne, P. E., Bouwman, J., Brookes, A. J., Clark, T., Crosas, M., Dillo, I., Dumon, O., Edmunds, S., Evelo, C. T., Finkers, R., Gonzalez-Beltran, A., Gray, A. J. G., Groth, P., Goble, C., Grethe, J. S., Heringa, J., 't Hoen, P. A. C., Hooft, R., Kuhn, T., Kok, R., Kok, J., Lusher, S. J., Martone, M. E., Mons, A., Packer, A. L., Persson, B., Rocca-Serra, P., Roos, M., van Schaik, R., Sansone, S.-A., Schultes, E., Sengstag, T., Slater, T., Strawn, G., Swertz, M. A., Thompson, M., van der Lei, J., van Mulligen, E., Velterop, J., Waagmeester, A., Wittenburg, P., Wolstencroft, K., Zhao, J., & Mons, B. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3(1), 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>
- 2 Aaron, J., & Chew, T.-L. (2021). A guide to accurate reporting in digital image processing – can anyone reproduce your quantitative analysis? *Journal of Cell Science*, 134(6), jcs.254151. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jcs.254151>
- 3 Rigano, A., Ehmsen, S., Öztürk, S. U., Ryan, J., Balashov, A., Hammer, M., Kirli, K., Boehm, U., Brown, C. M., Bellve, K., Chambers, J. J., Cosolo, A., Coleman, R. A., Faklaris, O., Fogarty, K. E., Guilbert, T., Hamacher, A. B., Itano, M. S., Keeley, D. P., Kunis, S., Lacoste, J., Laude, A., Ma, W. Y., Marcello, M., Montero-Llopis, P., Nelson, G., Nitschke, R., Pimentel, J. A., Weidtkamp-Peters, S., Park, P. J., Alver, B. H., Grunwald, D., & Strambio-De-Castillia, C. (2021). Micro-Meta App: an interactive tool for collecting microscopy metadata based on community specifications. *Nature Methods*, 18(12), 1489–1495. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01315-z>
- 4 Poger, D., Yen, L., & Braet, F. (2023). Big data in contemporary electron microscopy: challenges and opportunities in data transfer, compute and management. *Histochemistry and Cell Biology*, Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00418-023-02191-8>
- 5 Greenberg, J. (2017). Big Metadata, Smart Metadata, and Metadata Capital: Toward Greater Synergy Between Data Science and Metadata. *Journal of Data and Information Science*, 2(3), 19–36. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jdis-2017-0012>
- 6 Xie, I., & Matusiak, K. K. (2016). Chapter 5: Metadata. In I. Xie & K. K. Matusiak (Eds.), *Discover Digital Libraries* (pp. 129–170). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-417112-1.00005-3>
- 7 Bide, M. (2021). *Identifier and Metadata Standards in the Publishing Industry*. International Federation of Reproduction Rights Organisations (IFRRO) and International Publishers Association (IPA). https://ifrro.org/resources/documents/Booklets/public/MetadataStandards_23666.pdf
- 8 Little, A. (2018, May 29). *What Is Metadata? Enhance Your DAM System*. Retrieved April 4, 2023 from <https://datadwell.com/metadata-enhance-dam-system/>
- 9 Leipzig, J., Nüst, D., Hoyt, C. T., Ram, K., & Greenberg, J. (2021). The role of metadata in reproducible computational research. *Patterns*, 2(9), 100322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patter.2021.100322>
- 10 McCafferty, S., Poger, D., Yvette, W., Seal, C., Burgess, R., & Kenna, E. (2023). *Best Practices: PIDs for Instruments*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7759201>
- 11 Goodman, S. N., Fanelli, D., & Ioannidis, J. P. A. (2016). What does research reproducibility mean? *Science Translational Medicine*, 8(341), 341ps312. <https://doi.org/10.1126/scitranslmed.aaf5027>
- 12 Poger, D., van Schyndel, J., Nguyen, H., Silver, J., & Goscinski, W. J. (2021). *Orchestration and management of data generated by big-data electron microscopy instruments: A Discovery report*. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4744876>
- 13 Kunis, S., Hänsch, S., Schmidt, C., Wong, F., Strambio-De-Castillia, C., & Weidtkamp-Peters, S. (2021). MDEmic: a metadata annotation tool to facilitate management of FAIR image data in the bioimaging community. *Nature Methods*, 18(12), 1416–1417. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-021-01288-z>
- 14 Heddleston, J. M., Aaron, J. S., Khuon, S., & Chew, T.-L. (2021). A guide to accurate reporting in digital image acquisition – can anyone replicate your microscopy data? *Journal of Cell Science*, 134(6), jcs254144. <https://doi.org/10.1242/jcs.254144>
- 15 Nguyen, H. A. (2023). *Pitschi: A clowder-based end-to-end data management tool*. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7183431>
- 16 Marini, L., Gutierrez-Polo, I., Kooper, R., Satheesan, S. P., Burnette, M., Lee, J., Nicholson, T.,

- Zhao, Y., & McHenry, K. (2018). *Clowder: Open Source Data Management for Long Tail Data* PEARC'18, Pittsburgh, PA, USA. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3219104.3219159>
- 17 Jacobsen, A., de Miranda Azevedo, R., Juty, N., Batista, D., Coles, S., Cornet, R., Courtot, M., Crosas, M., Dumontier, M., Evelo, C. T., Goble, C., Guizzardi, G., Hansen, K. K., Hasnain, A., Hettne, K., Heringa, J., Hooft, R. W. W., Imming, M., Jeffery, K. G., Kaliyaperumal, R., Kersloot, M. G., Kirkpatrick, C. R., Kuhn, T., Labastida, I., Magagna, B., McQuilton, P., Meyers, N., Montesanti, A., van Reizen, M., Rocca-Serra, P., Pergl, R., Sansone, S.-A., da Silva Santos, L. O. B., Schneider, J., Strawn, G., Thompson, M., Waagmeester, A., Weigel, T., Wilkinson, M. D., Willighagen, E. L., Wittenburg, P., Roos, M., Mons, B., & Schultes, E. (2020). FAIR Principles: Interpretations and Implementation Considerations. *Data Intelligence*, 2(1–2), 10–29. https://doi.org/10.1162/dint_r_00024
 - 18 Meyer, G. R., Aragao, D., Mudie, N. J., Caradoc-Davies, T. T., McGowan, S., Bertling, P. J., Groenewegen, D., Quenette, S. M., Bond, C. S., Buckle, A. M., & Androulakis, S. (2014). Operation of the Australian Store.Synchrotron for macromolecular crystallography. *Acta Crystallographica Section D*, 70(10), 2510–2519. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1399004714016174>
 - 19 Mehnert, A. J., Janke, A., Gruwel, M., Goscinski, W. J., Close, T., Taylor, D., Narayanan, A., Vidalis, G., Galloway, G., & Treloar, A. (2019). Putting the Trust into Trusted Data Repositories: A Federated Solution for the Australian National Imaging Facility. *International Journal of Digital Curation*, 14(1), 102–113. <https://doi.org/10.2218/ijdc.v14i1.594>
 - 20 International Organization for Standardization. (2017). *Information and documentation — Records management processes — Metadata for records — Part 1: Principles (ISO 23081-1:2017)*. Retrieved April 22, 2023 from <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso:23081:-1:ed-2:v1:en>
 - 21 ANU Library. (n.d.). *Metadata Schemas*. Retrieved April 4, 2023 from <https://libguides.anu.edu.au/c.php?g=881167&p=6358464>
 - 22 Research Data Australia. (2022, November 18). *About RIF-CS*. Retrieved April 4, 2023 from <https://documentation.ardc.edu.au/display/DOC/About+RIF-CS>
 - 23 Deuble, R., Swingle, M., Stewart, D., & Yu, F. (2019). UQ Library's journey towards FAIR research outputs - Advancement of Research Data Management and Digitisation Services. 2019 International Association of Scientific and Technological University Libraries (IATUL) Conference, Perth, Australia.
 - 24 DataCite. (2021, March 30). *DataCite Metadata Schema*. Retrieved April 4, 2023 from <https://schema.datacite.org>
 - 25 Brase, J. (2009, 21-23 Nov. 2009). DataCite — A Global Registration Agency for Research Data. 2009 Fourth International Conference on Cooperation and Promotion of Information Resources in Science and Technology,
 - 26 DataCite Metadata Working Group. (2021). *DataCite Metadata Schema Documentation for the Publication and Citation of Research Data and Other Research Outputs. Version 4.4*. <https://doi.org/10.14454/3w3z-sa82>
 - 27 Allan, C., Burel, J.-M., Moore, J., Blackburn, C., Linkert, M., Loynton, S., MacDonald, D., Moore, W. J., Neves, C., Patterson, A., Porter, M., Tarkowska, A., Loranger, B., Avondo, J., Lagerstedt, I., Lianas, L., Leo, S., Hands, K., Hay, R. T., Patwardhan, A., Best, C., Kleywegt, G. J., Zanetti, G., & Swedlow, J. R. (2012). OMERO: flexible, model-driven data management for experimental biology. *Nature Methods*, 9(3), 245–253. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmeth.1896>
 - 28 Burel, J.-M., Besson, S., Blackburn, C., Carroll, M., Ferguson, R. K., Flynn, H., Gillen, K., Leigh, R., Li, S., Lindner, D., Linkert, M., Moore, W. J., Ramalingam, B., Rozbicki, E., Tarkowska, A., Walczysko, P., Allan, C., Moore, J., & Swedlow, J. R. (2015). Publishing and sharing multi-dimensional image data with OMERO. *Mammalian Genome*, 26(9), 441–447. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00335-015-9587-6>
 - 29 Li, S., Besson, S., Blackburn, C., Carroll, M., Ferguson, R. K., Flynn, H., Gillen, K., Leigh, R., Lindner, D., Linkert, M., Moore, W. J., Ramalingam, B., Rozbicki, E., Rustici, G., Tarkowska, A., Walczysko, P., Williams, E., Allan, C., Burel, J.-M., Moore, J., & Swedlow, J. R. (2016). Metadata management for high content screening in OMERO. *Methods*, 96, 27–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymeth.2015.10.006>